

Analysis of online reviews of hotels in the Cabo Branco District, Paraíba, Brazil

Brenda Araújo¹, Adriana Brambilla²

¹ Paraíba Federal University, João Pessoa, Paraíba, Brazil

² Paraíba Federal University, João Pessoa, Paraíba, Brazil/GCET

³ UNIFUTURO, João Pessoa, Paraíba, Brazil/GCET

⁴ Paraná Estadual University, Apucarana, Paraná, Brazil//GCET

⁵ Pernambuco Federal University, Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil//GCET

Corresponding author: Felipe Gomes do Nascimento (felipegomes.14@hotmail.com)

Abstract

The addressed theme focused on the importance of online reviews in contemporary hotel industry, emphasizing the crucial role customers play in sharing their opinions and experiences through review platforms. Therefore, the research aimed to contribute to the improvement of hotel services by highlighting the relevance of perceived quality in various aspects, such as location, comfort, cleanliness, cost-benefit, and Wi-Fi availability. In this context, the main objective of this article was to analyze the most present positive and negative factors in online reviews of hotels in the Cabo Branco district, Paraíba. Regarding the methodological approach, reviews of hotels listed on the Booking and TripAdvisor platforms were collected and analyzed, focusing on the Cabo Branco district, PB. The results revealed that location, cleanliness, and Wi-Fi quality emerged as the main positive aspects highlighted by customers, while cost-benefit and the amount paid for the service were pointed out as the main negative factors. For future research, it is recommended to conduct longitudinal studies to monitor the evolution of reviews over time, as well as a more in-depth investigation into the factors that influence customer satisfaction in the hotel industry. This includes aspects such as organizational culture, customer experience, and technological innovations. These approaches can provide valuable insights for the development of effective management strategies and the improvement of hotel service quality.

Key words: Lodging establishments, booking.com, quality, tripadvisor

Subject editor:

Desislava Varadzhakova

Received: 19 May 2025

Accepted: 14 August 2025

Published: 27 October 2025

Citation: Araújo B, Brambilla A, Vanzella E, Gomes do Nascimento F, Fernandes Carvalho de Melo P (2025) Analysis of online reviews of hotels in the Cabo Branco District, Paraíba, Brazil. *GeoStudies* 2: 67–83. <https://doi.org/10.3897/geostudies.2.e159500>

Copyright: © Brenda Araújo et al.

This is an open access article distributed under terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License ([Attribution 4.0 International – CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)).

Introduction

A customer evaluation of a product or service has a direct influence on the purchasing decisions of many consumers. These opinions serve as a means to assess, to a certain extent, the quality of products or services and thus influence decision-making by relying on the experiences of those who have already used or acquired a good.

For companies, the use of these evaluation tools, in addition to conveying trust, is a valuable reference base, as they offer indicators of which aspects

can be improved (Petry et al. 2016), since the platforms give customers the opportunity to share their opinions online.

These reviews have become more rapidly disseminated and highly visible to those interested in learning about services, establishments, and products. For lodging establishments, reviews are the key to building a good reputation and attracting guests, as they reflect customer impressions of the services provided.

According to a study conducted by Capterra (2019), 69% of internet users prefer to consult reviews from other buyers rather than rely on expert opinions. These perspectives significantly influence the decision of potential customers, which can lead to the acquisition of new consumers or, conversely, negatively impact the choice of a lodging establishment.

In this context, the question this research aims to answer is: What are the main factors that influence online reviews made by tourists about hotels located in the Cabo Branco neighborhood of João Pessoa (PB), Brazil?

Thus, the general objective of the study is to analyze the most prevalent positive and negative factors in online reviews of hotels in the Cabo Branco district of João Pessoa, Paraíba, Brazil.

Theoretical framework

From the consumer's perspective, the perception of quality is intrinsically linked to the evaluations they provide regarding a given service. In this context of product improvement, as noted by Souza (2018), the first discussions on the concepts and principles of quality emerged in the 1930s in the United States and in the 1940s in Japan. Thus, the concepts of quality emerged, with notable contributions from Juran (1951), Ishikawa (1993), Armand Feigenbaum (1994), and Deming (1993).

According to Deming (1993), quality is understood as all improvements made to a product based on customer perceptions. Juran (1951), in turn, shares a similar perspective to Deming (1993) but diverges by emphasizing the importance of customer satisfaction and needs, advocating for the implementation of changes to ensure the satisfaction of these needs.

Ishikawa (1993) highlights the importance of quality from the product planning stage, understanding it as a synonym for the process that encompasses everything from the conception to the commercialization of a useful, economical, and consistently satisfactory product for consumers. On the other hand, Feigenbaum (1994) emphasizes that quality is intrinsically related to the corrections made to products, which have a direct influence on consumer satisfaction.

As a result, quality has also been incorporated into lodging establishments as a competitive advantage. Beyond merely attracting new guests, it is essential to offer high-quality products and services.

Lodging establishments are also part of the tourism infrastructure, marketed within the tourism sector. In this regard, there is a need to assess the quality of service delivery, since the quality of experiences has an important impact on guest satisfaction. It is through these experiences that guests convert their stay into something unforgettable.

In the hotel industry, quality is based on service and is measured through customer satisfaction (Magalhães et al. 2020), that is, whether or not the customer expectations have been met. According to Surprenant and Churchill (1982), customer expectations have a significant influence on the anticipated

performance of a product or service. In this context, when a potential guest searches for lodging on a booking website and comes across a hotel, they are exposed to the ratings and comments attributed to the establishment. From that moment on, the customer may create certain expectations, which can vary from high to low. These expectations are automatically associated with the services and infrastructure offered by the hotel, resulting in a preliminary judgment about the quality of the service, even before its effective use.

In this scenario, service performance is influenced by customer expectations, determining an initial perception of its quality, whether positive or negative. Therefore, it is crucial to maintain a balance between customer expectations and company performance, as highlighted by Kotler (1999).

It is also important to consider that the concept of service quality is subjective, as quality can be measured by various factors such as customer service, safety, cost, cleanliness, comfort, product and service quality, among others. The scale of importance of these factors is associated with the individual needs of each customer (Carvalho and Paladini 2012).

Therefore, every detail within the company during the guest's stay becomes a factor to assess the quality of the lodging establishment. In this context, the perception of individual attributes can be influenced by general impressions, just as strong impressions of one attribute can shape the perception of all others, and these impressions are directly related to consumer satisfaction.

According to Gianesi and Corrêa (2006), the perception of quality is established every time the customer interacts with the service provider. The same authors also state that perceived quality can be influenced both by the service delivery itself and by the communication conveyed to the customer. In this regard, quality in the hotel sector represents the incessant pursuit of meeting customer needs and satisfying their expectations through continuous improvement of the services provided. Online reviews in the hotel sector through digital platforms.

The evolution of communication and information technologies has brought significant changes for companies. The development of search engines on the internet has enabled greater access to information, granting tourists an expanded power of choice.

However, determining whether the chosen lodging establishment meets individual needs has become more challenging. In this context, the positive and negative factors highlighted in online reviews play a crucial role for hotel managers.

These reviews are provided by customers who have experienced the stay at a chosen establishment, sharing their perceptions and expectations about the place with a broad audience. This sharing process allows future guests to conduct a preliminary assessment of the lodging establishment, thereby influencing the decision-making process of potential customers.

According to Castelli (2010), when travelers check into a hotel, they bring with them a range of needs, desires, and expectations while simultaneously entrusting the hotel with the responsibility of fulfilling them. In this context, users increasingly become protagonists in the online purchasing process, as providing information about their experience with a particular product or service will influence the final decision of potential future customers, as well as contributing to the development of the company's online reputation (Yacouel and Fleischer, 2012). For this reason, lodging establishment managers must pay close attention to the factors that stand out in reviews, that is, those that

have the greatest positive or negative impact on guests (Bandeira and Menezes, 2022). In recent years, online travel agencies such as Booking.com and travel websites like TripAdvisor have gained significant popularity among tourists. Petry et al. (2016) explain that the online travel agency (OTA) Booking.com stands out as the leading platform for lodging-related information. On this site, only guests who have made reservations and stayed at a property through the OTA are allowed to review the services provided. After checkout, guests are invited to evaluate their experience, which reinforces the credibility of the published reviews.

In addition, Booking.com and TripAdvisor are quality assessment tools that support managers and assist in the supervision of services regarding facilities, service, and products offered (Zhou et al. 2014).

Booking.com is an online travel agency founded in 1996 in Amsterdam as a startup by Geert-Jan Bruinsma. Initially, the site only allowed reservations at a local hotel in the Netherlands, but with growth, international listings were introduced, attracting Kees Koolen as an investor.

In 2005, the platform was acquired by the US-based company Priceline, a global leader in online travel reservations. As a result, Booking.com became one of the largest travel e-commerce companies in the world. The platform offers booking services for accommodations, flights, and even car rentals. With a global reach, the website is available in 43 languages and features over 28 million accommodation listings, including more than 6.2 million houses, apartments, and other lodging options worldwide.

The review system on Booking.com stands out for its reliability and authenticity, since only guests who have actually made reservations and completed their stays through the platform are authorized to leave feedback.

This post-checkout evaluation system ensures that opinions and ratings reflect genuine and verified experiences. Guests can rate various aspects of their stay, including staff, comfort, free Wi-Fi, amenities, value for money, cleanliness, and location.

According to the online platform Mundo das Marcas, TripAdvisor was founded in February 2000 by Steve Kaufer, Langley Steinert, Nick Shanny, and Thomas Palka. The idea for the site originated from Kaufer and his wife's personal experience searching for travel options through traditional travel agencies. The couple noticed a uniformity in the information available, with websites presenting similar photos, descriptions, and information. In response to the limited range of diverse and authentic lodging experiences, Kaufer and his co-founders launched the platform to provide a solution (Mundo das Marcas, 2022).

As a result, TripAdvisor.com has become a travel guidance platform that provides detailed information and reviews on a wide range of tourism services. Users contribute with comments, opinions and tips about hotels, restaurants, tourist attractions, and other services. Guests can rate various aspects of their experience, including location, cleanliness, service and value, using a 0 to 5 scale.

In 2004, the company was acquired by InterActiveCorp (IAC), an American internet company. Currently, TripAdvisor has over 1 billion reviews and ratings, operating in 43 markets and available in 22 languages. This vast amount of data, combined with its global accessibility, make TripAdvisor a reliable and indispensable source of information for travelers worldwide.

From the sand to the promenade: Hotels and the Cabo Branco beachfront, João Pessoa (PB), Brazil

Cabo Branco Beach, located in João Pessoa, the capital of Paraíba, is a popular urban beach frequented by locals and tourists visiting the city. In addition to the traditional sea bathing activities, Cabo Branco Beach offers a variety of sports options, such as soccer and volleyball, which can be enjoyed along its extensive stretch of sand. Furthermore, the promenade along the beach provides an ideal space for physical activities, including walking, cycling, and rollerblading. This diversity of leisure and sports possibilities is highly attractive and versatile for different audiences.

According to the João Pessoa City Hall, "the hotel network in João Pessoa has more than 14,000 beds available" (PMJP, 2018). Regarding the lodging establishments located in the Cabo Branco district, the Registry of Tourism Service Providers (Cadastur) indicates the existence of approximately 23 registered establishments, 12 of which are classified as hotels and were the object of analysis in this research (CADASTUR, 2023).

The choice of Cabo Branco Beach as the focus of this study is due to its status as one of the most popular urban beaches in the city, characterized by intense tourist activity. This popularity makes Cabo Branco a place of significant interest for the investigation of lodging and tourism dynamics.

Methodology

The research has a descriptive nature, which is a type of study aimed at describing the characteristics of a given population or phenomenon or establishing relationships between variables.

Regarding the study approach, it is a quantitative research, as it involved surveys on the number of hotels registered on the official CADASTUR website, along with a statistical analysis of the average ratings on the Booking and TripAdvisor platforms.

The bibliographic research was conducted based on authors and papers discussing topics such as quality, service quality, consumer behavior, and hospitality in service management. Moreover, searches were carried out on the Booking and TripAdvisor websites.

Data collection on the aforementioned websites consisted of stages. Initially, a survey of hotels located at Cabo Branco Beach, in the city of João Pessoa (PB), registered with CADASTUR was carried out.

CADASTUR is a system developed by the Ministry of Tourism in collaboration with regulatory bodies, whereby individuals and legal entities operating in the tourism sector register aim to promote the formalization and inspection of tourism services in Brazil.

As a result, a total of 12 hotels were identified. These establishments were analyzed to identify the most frequently mentioned positive factors in guest reviews, as well as the most frequently cited negative factors. The reviews were collected through the evaluation methods of Booking.com and TripAdvisor.

During March 2023, a comprehensive analysis was conducted on the overall ratings and specific areas on each platform, along with user reviews published on Booking.com and TripAdvisor. In addition to identifying the positive and negative

factors mentioned by reviewers of these 12 hotels, a statistical analysis was performed to compare the average ratings on the Booking and TripAdvisor platforms.

This procedure aimed to verify the existence of significant differences between the average ratings on the two platforms, providing a deeper understanding of users' perceptions of the lodging services offered at Cabo Branco Beach.

It is important to note that, in the statistical analysis, the comparison was performed only on the criteria common to both platforms. Since Booking includes additional criteria, these were not considered in the statistical comparison process.

Following the statistical analysis, detailed discussions and comments on the overall ratings are presented, as well as a detailed analysis of the positive and negative factors unique to each platform.

The following tables (Table 1 and Table 2) show the overall scores and evaluations of the specific areas of each platform (Booking and TripAdvisor), referring to the hotels located in Cabo Branco and listed on CADASTUR, providing a basis for the statistical analysis of the average ratings on both platforms.

Table 1. Hotel Ratings on Booking.

BOOKING	OVERALL RATING
ATLÂNTICO CABO BRANCO	8.6
BA'RA HOTEL	9.3
ESCUNA PRAIA HOTEL	7.3
HOTEL SOLMAR	8.1
LITTORAL HOTEL	7.9
NETUANAH PRAIA HOTEL	8.3
NORD EASY ONDAS DO ATLÂNTICO	8.1
ALTIPLANO HOTEL	7.7
ORIENTAL PRAIA HOTEL	8.5
SKYLER MAR HOTEL	8.4
VAL ATLANTIC HOTEL	8.6
XENIUS HOTEL	-

Source: Research data, 2023.

Table 2. Hotel Ratings on Tripadvisor.

TRIPADVISOR	OVERALL RATING
ATLÂNTICO CABO BRANCO	4
BA'RA HOTEL	5
ESCUNA PRAIA HOTEL	2,5
HOTEL SOLMAR	3,5
LITTORAL HOTEL	4
NETUANAH PRAIA HOTEL	3,5
NORD EASY ONDAS DO ATLÂNTICO	4
ALTIPLANO HOTEL	3,5
ORIENTAL PRAIA HOTEL	4,5
SKYLER MAR HOTEL	4
VAL ATLANTIC HOTEL	4,5
XENIUS HOTEL	3,5

Source: Research data, 2023.

Due to discrepancies in the evaluation methodology adopted by the two platforms, given that Booking uses a 0 to 10 rating scale, while TripAdvisor adopts a 0 to 5, it was necessary to transform the data from TripAdvisor in order to standardize the evaluation scales. These adjusted ratings were then used in the statistical tests conducted.

In order to investigate whether the averages of the overall ratings attributed to the hotels were similar across the two platforms, a t-test (Student's t-distribution) was performed (Table 3). This test is suitable for small, independent samples with distinct variances and it is widely recognized for its robustness and effectiveness in comparing means in contexts similar to this study.

Hypotheses tested: H0: The means of the overall ratings on both sites are equal and H1: The means of the overall ratings on both sites are different.

Table 3. Results of the t-test for overall rating averages.

T-test: Two-sample assuming distinct variances.		
	BOOKING	TRIPADVISOR
Average	8,254545455	7,818181818
Variance	0,280727273	1,763636364
Observations	11	11
Hypothesis of difference of means	0	
Gl	13	
Stat t	1,012198807	
P(T<=t) one-tailed	0,164956178	
t critical one-tailed	1,770933396	
P(T<=t) two-tailed	0,329912356	
t critical two-tailed	2,160368656	

Source: Authors,2023.

It is relevant to point out that the Xênus Hotel was not considered in the statistical test, since no scores associated with it were identified on the Booking website. This exclusion is essential to guarantee the integrity and validity of the results obtained in the comparative analysis of the overall rating averages between the two platforms.

Upon conducting the statistical test, it was found that the p-value was calculated to be 0.16, which exceeds the established significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. This result suggests that no statistically significant evidence exists to reject the null hypothesis (H0), which states that the average overall ratings given by guests on the two websites are equivalent.

According to the results obtained from the statistical test, the one-tailed critical t-value was calculated as 1.77, while the resulting t-statistic was 1.01, revealing itself to be lower than the critical value and, therefore, falling within the acceptance region of the null hypothesis (H0). Similarly, for the two-tailed critical t-test, the critical value was 2.16, while the resulting t-statistic was 1.01, also remaining below the critical value and, consequently, within the acceptance region of the null hypothesis (H0). These findings corroborate the hypothesis that the average overall ratings given by users on both websites are equivalent.

Following this, a comparison of the evaluation criteria considered by guests was conducted, revealing four shared factors between the two websites. These elements include factors related to staff, cleanliness, cost-benefit ratio, and the location of the establishments.

Next, a further transformation of the data from TripAdvisor was necessary to ensure the compatibility of the rating scales used on both platforms. This step was crucial to ensure the comparability and consistency of the analyses, allowing for a robust and accurate evaluation of the common items across the review websites.

The four items—staff, cleanliness, cost-benefit ratio, and location—were analyzed individually, and the results of the statistical tests confirmed the hypothesis that the average overall ratings on websites are equivalent. The evaluations of these elements, present on both platforms, revealed mean scores without statistically significant differences, confirming that any unfavorable reviews given by guests are not associated with the evaluation platform but rather with the specific characteristics of the evaluated hotel.

Results and discussions

After completing the statistical analysis related to the average rating scores on both platforms, an individualized analysis of the following topics was conducted: overall ratings, negative factors, and positive factors recorded on each platform. This approach allowed for a detailed and in-depth evaluation of users' perceptions regarding the hotel establishments, highlighting specific and distinct nuances within each evaluative context.

Table 4 shows the overall ratings for each hotel on the Booking platform.

Table 4. Booking overall rating.

OVERALL RATING - BOOKING		
HOTEL	RATING	CLASSIFICATION
ATLÂNTICO CABO BRANCO	8,6	Fabulous
BA'RA HOTEL	9,3	Fantastic
ESCUNA PRAIA HOTEL	7,3	Good
HOTEL SOLMAR	8,1	Very good
LITTORAL HOTEL	7,9	Good
NETUANAH PRAIA HOTEL	8,3	Very good
NORD EASY ONDAS DO ATLÂNTICO	8,1	Very good
ALTIPLANO HOTEL	7,7	Good
ORIENTAL PRAIA HOTEL	8,5	Very good
SKYLER MAR HOTEL	8,4	Very good
VAL ATLANTIC HOTEL	8,6	Fabulous
XENIUS HOTEL	Not found	Not found

Source: Authors, 2023.

Among the twelve hotels analyzed, Ba'ra Hotel stands out with the highest overall rating. Recognized as a luxury establishment, Ba'ra Hotel was inaugurated in 2022 and offers a range of services, including spa, tour packages, swimming pools, and gourmet dining experiences.

The high rating attributed to Ba'ra Hotel suggests that the establishment offers exceptional quality service, capable of satisfying its guests and meeting the expectations set by the company.

The table 5 presents the main positive aspects observed in hotels using the Booking.com platform. For analysis purposes, all reviews that received a score of 7.0 or higher were considered positive. This classification was adopted because, generally speaking, a rating of 70% or higher is widely accepted as indicative of a satisfactory guest experience. In other words, when a hotel receives a rating of 7.0 or higher, it typically reflects that the majority of guests were satisfied with their stay, whether regarding service, cleanliness, location, or other aspects evaluated.

Table 5. Positive factors on Booking.

BOOKING POSITIVE FACTORS							
HOTEL/NAME OF THE FOUNDATION	Staff	Convenience	Cleanliness	Comfort	Cost-benefit ratio	Location	Wifi
ATLÂNTICO CABO BRANCO	9,1	8,6	8,9	8,8	8,0	8,1	7,6
BA'RA HOTEL	9,6	9,4	9,7	9,6	8,5	9,6	9,8
ESCUNA PRAIA HOTEL	8,3	*	7,4	*	7,6	9,6	8,2
HOTEL SOLMAR	9,2	8,1	8,8	8,4	8,0	8,8	9,2
LITTORAL HOTEL	8,7	7,6	8,1	7,9	7,6	9,4	*
NETUANAH PRAIA HOTEL	8,9	7,9	8,4	8,3	8,0	9,4	7,9
NORD EASY ONDAS DO ATLÂNTICO	8,7	8,1	8,3	8,4	7,9	9,6	7,9
ORIENTAL HOTEL/ ALTIPLANO HOTEL	8,7	7,5	7,8	7,6	7,2	*	7,6
ORIENTAL PRAIA HOTEL	9,1	8,7	8,7	8,7	8,0	8,2	8,3
SKYLER MAR HOTEL/HOTEL NORD LUXXOR CABO BRANCO	8,8	8,4	8,7	8,6	7,9	9,5	7,7
VAL ATLANTIC HOTEL	9,0	8,6	8,8	8,7	8,3	8,6	7,5
XENIUS HOTEL	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

Source: Research data, 2023.

On the other hand, Table 6 highlights the negative factors identified in the hotels through the Booking platform. For this analysis, ratings lower than 6.9 were considered negative factors, as a rating of 70% or higher, that is, equal to or above 7.0, is widely recognized as an indicator of a satisfactory guest experience. Therefore, ratings below 7.0 were classified as negative or poorly rated, according to the established criteria.

Figure 1 presents the percentages and average ratings of specific areas for the eleven establishments listed on the Booking platform.

Based on the analysis of Figure 1, as well as Tables 5 and 6, it can be observed that among the positive factors, those that stood out the most and received the highest ratings in the guest evaluations were: staff, location, and cleanliness.

According to Giansesi and Corrêa (2006), the perception of quality is established at every moment the customer interacts with the service provider. In other words, the treatment and communication during customer service by the staff, play a significant role in shaping evaluations of the establishment.

Thus, in the hotel sector, reception, the first point of interaction with the guest, plays a fundamental role and it is often regarded as the "heart and lungs" of a hotel. Therefore, maintaining attentive and courteous staff provides guests

with a sense of security and comfort during their stay. Furthermore, in cases of unforeseen circumstances or inquiries, quality customer service ensures that guests feel welcomed and satisfied with the establishment.

As an example of satisfaction related to staff, a guest review on the Booking platform regarding one of the analyzed hotels can be cited. This example illustrates the importance of high-quality service in shaping the overall guest experience (Figure 2).

As for the staff factor, cleanliness also stands out among the positive factors. For a hotel, maintaining excellent cleanliness and hygiene throughout the establishment is essential. The goal of housekeeping is to deliver sanitized and guest-ready rooms, in addition to performing regular cleaning of occupied rooms (Sidônio 2015).

Table 6. Negative factors on Booking.

HOTEL/NAME OF THE FOUNDATION	Staff	Convenience	Cleanliness	Comfort	Cost-benefit ratio	Location	Wifi
ATLÂNTICO CABO BRANCO	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
BA'RA HOTEL	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
ESCUNA PRAIA HOTEL	*	6,8	*	6,8	*	*	*
HOTEL SOLMAR	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
LITTORAL HOTEL	*	*	*	*	*	*	6,3
NETUANAH PRAIA HOTEL	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
NORD EASY ONDAS DO ATLÂNTICO	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
ORIENTAL HOTEL/ ALTIPLANO HOTEL					*	6,9	
ORIENTAL PRAIA HOTEL	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
SKYLER MAR HOTEL/HOTEL NORD LUXXOR CABO BRANCO	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
VAL ATLANTIC HOTEL	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
XENIUS HOTEL	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

Source: Authors, 2023.

Figure 1. Average Ratings of Specific Areas on Booking. Source: Research data, 2023.

Excellence

Everything is very tasteful and the service is excellent! The staff is always helpful and attentive. The breakfast is the best.

Figure 2. Example of a guest review. Source: Screenshot from the Booking.com website, 2023.

Another factor that stood out positively was the location. Location is strategically important both for the hotel and for meeting guests' needs, such as dining, sightseeing, shopping, and other activities. The hotel must be close to establishments such as restaurants, drugstores, banks, laundromats, and 24-hour service stations. In addition, proximity to leisure areas, tourist attractions, the city center, and a safe location are equally important.

The convenience of having everything nearby creates a sense of satisfaction and practicality for travelers. Thus, the hotel's location not only enhances the guest experience but also contributes to the financial sustainability of the business. This can be observed in a customer satisfaction review collected from the Booking platform, related to the location factor of one of the hotels analyzed (Figure 3).

Great location!

The location is perfect! Close to everything, you don't need a car for anything, you can walk everywhere, there are good restaurants just a step away from the hotel, and the beach in front is pretty good too!

Figure 3. Example of a guest review. Source: Screenshot from the Booking.com website, 2023.

A negative aspect identified in the evaluations was the quality of the hotel's Wi-Fi, as the Wi-Fi network is frequently mentioned among the negative factors on the Booking platform. This issue is particularly relevant for corporate guests, who rely on the Internet for both professional activities and their overall stay. Since they tend to use the internet more than other guests, Wi-Fi quality becomes a top priority.

In the current context, where the world is strongly driven by digitalization and internet connectivity, providing a high-quality Wi-Fi network offers customers peace of mind and reliability, ensuring seamless access to the virtual world. Moreover, through internet access, guests can search for information about tourist attractions, restaurants, transportation options, and details about places they plan to visit. Therefore, Wi-Fi quality is a crucial factor in ensuring the satisfaction and convenience of corporate travelers.

Another negative factor identified in the analysis was comfort. Comfort can be defined as the feeling of being welcomed and relaxed in an environment. This perception is influenced by several elements, including lighting, acoustics, and temperature, among others.

Therefore, ensuring that the guest room is cozy and comfortable is essential. Hotels should prioritize guests' overall comfort, considering that most travelers seek lodging primarily for rest and leisure.

For instance, a guest expressed dissatisfaction with the comfort level through a review on the Booking platform regarding one of the hotels analyzed

(Figure 4). This type of feedback highlights the importance of continuous improvements to ensure guest satisfaction and, consequently, maintain a good reputation in the market.

Bad
Of all the inconveniences, the breakfast was awful. I think the hotel should be more attentive, as its location is excellent.

Figure 4. Example of a guest review. Source: Screenshot from the Booking.com website, 2023.

Table 7. Tripadvisor overall rating.

OVERALL RATING - TRIPADVISOR		
HOTEL	RATING	CLASSIFICATION
ATLÂNTICO CABO BRANCO	4.0	Very good
BA'RA HOTEL	5.0	Excellent
ESCUNA PRAIA HOTEL	2.5	Average
HOTEL SOLMAR	3.5	Very good
LITTORAL HOTEL	4.0	Very good
NETUANAH PRAIA HOTEL	3.5	Very good
NORD EASY ONDAS DO ATLÂNTICO	4.0	Very good
ORIENTAL HOTEL/ ALTIPLANO HOTEL	3.5	Very good
ORIENTAL PRAIA HOTEL	4.5	Excellent
SKYLER MAR HOTEL	4.0	Very good
VAL ATLANTIC HOTEL	4.5	Excellent
XENIUS HOTEL	3.5	Very good

Source: Author, 2023.

Table 7 presents the overall rating of each hotel on the Tripadvisor platform.

As on Booking.com, the Ba'ra Hotel stands out with the highest rating, 9.3, being classified as "fantastic" on the site. Following closely are the Val Atlantic Hotel, located opposite Cabo Branco Beach, and the Oriental Praia Hotel, a luxurious hotel with 60 rooms located one block from the beach.

Table 8 below presents the positive factors of the hotels as evaluated on the Tripadvisor platform. In this analysis, ratings of 3.5 or higher were considered positive factors. A score of 70% or higher, equivalent to a rating of 3.5 or above, is regarded as good.

Table 9 presents a detailed analysis of the negative factors of the hotels as evaluated on the Tripadvisor platform. For this analysis, all evaluations with ratings lower than 3.5 were considered negative factors. This classification is based on the understanding that a score of 70% or higher, that is, equal to or higher than 3.5, is considered a good evaluation. Therefore, evaluations with scores lower than 3.5 are indicative of unsatisfactory performance. This approach allows for a precise identification of aspects that require improvement to enhance guest satisfaction.

Figure 5 provides a detailed analysis of the percentages and average ratings across various specific areas of the twelve establishments evaluated on the Tripadvisor platform. This visual representation enables a better understanding of the different performance dimensions of the hotels, offering a comparative view of their strengths and weaknesses.

Table 8. Positive factors on Tripadvisor.

TRIPADVISOR POSITIVE FACTORS				
HOTEL/NAME OF THE FOUNDATION	Location	Cleanliness	Service	Rating
ATLÂNTICO CABO BRANCO	4.0	4,3	4.2	3.8
BA'RA HOTEL	5,0	4.8	5.0	4.8
ESCUNA PRAIA HOTEL	4,6	*	*	*
HOTEL SOLMAR	4,2	4.1	3.9	3.8
LITTORAL HOTEL	4,6	4.1	4.2	3.9
NETUANAH PRAIA HOTEL	4,4	3.6	3.7	3.6
NORD EASY ONDAS DO ATLÂNTICO	4,6	4.3	4.2	4.0
ORIENTAL HOTEL/ ALTIPLANO HOTEL	*	4,8	4.1	*
ORIENTAL PRAIA HOTEL	4.3	4.8	5,0	5,0
SKYLER MAR HOTEL/HOTEL NORD LUXXOR CABO BRANCO	4,5	4.4	4.2	3.8
VAL ATLANTIC HOTEL	4.3	4,7	4,7	4.5
XENIUS HOTEL	4,8	3.9	3.8	3.8

Source: Authors, 2023.

Table 9. Negative factors on Tripadvisor.

TRIPADVISOR NEGATIVE FACTORS				
HOTEL/NAME OF THE FOUNDATION	Location	Cleanliness	Service	Rating
ATLÂNTICO CABO BRANCO	*	*	*	*
BA'RA HOTEL	*	*	*	*
ESCUNA PRAIA HOTEL	*	2.6	3.2	2.8
HOTEL SOLMAR	*	*	*	*
LITTORAL HOTEL	*	*	*	*
NETUANAH PRAIA HOTEL	*	*	*	*
NORD EASY ONDAS DO ATLÂNTICO	*	*	*	*
ORIENTAL HOTEL/ ALTIPLANO HOTEL	3.0	*	*	3.3
ORIENTAL PRAIA HOTEL	*	*	*	*
SKYLER MAR HOTEL/HOTEL NORD LUXXOR CABO BRANCO	*	*	*	*
VAL ATLANTIC HOTEL	*	*	*	*
XENIUS HOTEL	*	*	*	*

Source: Authors, 2023.

Figure 5. Average Ratings of Specific Areas on Tripadvisor. Source: Research data, 2023.

By analyzing Figure 5 along with Tables 08 and 09, it becomes evident that cleanliness and location stand out among the positive factors, even with a below-average rating in one of the establishments. These aspects show the highest percentage of positive reviews, indicating that lower ratings are somewhat punctual and do not reflect the overall trend of the evaluated establishments. This observation is corroborated by the tie in averages and percentages across the charts.

To illustrate this analysis, a simple and concise review regarding satisfaction with cleanliness was collected from a comment left by a guest on the Tripadvisor platform (Figure 6). This example highlights the importance of cleanliness as a key factor in guests' positive perceptions, reinforcing the need for continuous attention to this aspect in order to maintain high-quality standards in hotel services.

*Excellent hotel
Clean, organized hotel, spectacular service, ample parking, and the room I stayed in had a lovely little balcony. Breakfast had plenty of options. I'll definitely be back soon.*

Figure 6. Example of a guest review.

Similar to the analysis on Booking.com, value stands out as the most negative aspect, receiving the lowest ratings and averages in both evaluations. The cost-benefit and value categories presented the lowest percentage of positive evaluations, indicating that guest expectations at some hotels were not fully met. These expectations were related to the price of lodging and the promises made by the company, which, however, did not deliver a service proportional to the amount charged. Thus, it is evident that the service provided was considered as overpriced in relation to its cost.

To conclude the analysis, a negative review related to cost-benefit was selected. This comment, made by a guest on the Tripadvisor platform about one of the hotels studied, illustrates the frustration caused by the perception of a high value for the service provided (Figure 7).

*Terrible value for money
The prices are too high for the hotel's standard. It needs painting and maintenance throughout. The bathroom has mold on the walls. The air conditioning doesn't cool well. The bedroom door rattles all night (it had to be propped open to stop it from slamming in the wind). The rooms are small. The only positives are: a good location, good Wi-Fi, and free on-site parking.*

Figure 7. Example of a guest review. Source: Screenshot from the Tripadvisor website, 2023.

Conclusions

The pursuit of quality must be constant, and the hotel industry is no exception. Hotel services advertised on platforms such as Booking and Tripadvisor are evaluated by customers based on their experiences at the establishments. These evaluations reflect whether guest expectations were met, indicating the quality of the service provided.

In this regard, this article aimed to analyze the most prevalent positive and negative factors in online reviews of hotels located in the Cabo Branco district, PB. Location, staff, and cleanliness emerge as strategic and highly significant factors. These aspects are often highlighted as positive in user comments on both Booking and Tripadvisor, underscoring their importance in service delivery.

These aspects are directly related to the guest reception process, both in terms of human interaction, with the presence of well-trained and attentive staff, and in the physical and operational aspects of the hotel infrastructure. Ensuring that rooms meet expected quality standards, particularly regarding cleanliness and organization, is fundamental (Castelli, 2003; Sidónio, 2015). Therefore, attention to these factors is essential to ensure a positive guest experience and to continuously improve the quality of hotel services.

On the other hand, it is crucial to highlight the perspectives of cost-benefit and value offered to the customer at the time of purchase. These factors were negatively highlighted in the comments analyzed, emphasizing the importance of how tourists perceive the fairness of the amount paid for the service.

Given this perception, hotel managers must adopt greater caution when determining pricing strategies. In addition, it is essential to maintain the quality of the hotel infrastructure and the services provided. This approach not only ensures a fairer balance between cost and benefit but also helps minimize frustrations arising from expectations created about cost-benefit and value during the booking process.

Regarding the negative factors, a key element stands out as indispensable, particularly in reviews posted on Booking: Wi-Fi quality. This issue is a significant source of dissatisfaction and frustration among hotel guests. Offering a robust and stable internet connection, whether for work-related activities or entertainment, has become a crucial factor in attracting customers. Therefore, it is the responsibility of hotel managers to carefully select reliable internet service providers and ensure proper maintenance of the network to enhance the overall guest experience.

Therefore, in general, it is observed that customers adopt a very critical stance in their reviews. They do not hesitate to openly and thoroughly express both the strengths and weaknesses of their experiences. These reviews play a crucial role in providing establishments with a clear understanding of the positive and negative aspects of their services. Such analyses can be decisive for the success of a hotel, as long as managers take concrete measures to reinforce well-rated aspects and address identified shortcomings. However, if hotel administrators fail to respond effectively to these evaluations, the operation and long-term sustainability of their lodging establishments may be compromised.

This means that the average overall ratings given by guests on the two websites are equivalent. In other words, the hotel ratings on both websites are considered to be similar. Thus, if unfavorable reviews have occurred, they cannot be attributed to the nature of the type of guest but rather to potential deficiencies or specific issues associated with the evaluated establishments.

Finally, given these considerations, it is the responsibility of lodging establishments to meet customer demands through regular monitoring of reviews and the implementation of strategies that lead to service improvements. The ultimate goal is to meet or even exceed guest expectations, thereby striving to achieve the highest possible level of quality.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Adriana Brambilla <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5603-4195>

Elidio Vanzella <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6217-4722>

Felipe Gomes do Nascimento <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4881-1385>

Priscila Fernandes Carvalho de Melo <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5296-933X>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Booking.Com. Tudo o que você precisa saber sobre as Notas de Avaliação dos Hóspedes. <https://partner.booking.com/pt-br/ajuda/avalia%C3%A7%C3%B5es-dos-h%C3%B3spedes/geral/tudo-o-que-voc%C3%AA-precisa-saber-sobre-notas-de-avalia%C3%A7%C3%A3o-dos-0>
- Cadastro de Prestadores de Serviços Turístico [Cadastur] (2022a) Hotéis em Cabo Branco, João Pessoa, Paraíba. <https://cadastur.turismo.gov.br/hotsite/#!/public/sou-turista/inicio>
- Cadastro de Prestadores de Serviços Turístico [Cadastur] (2022b) Informações e dúvidas frequentes. <https://cadastur.turismo.gov.br/hotsite/#!/public/duvidas-frequentes/inicio>
- Capterra (2019) Avaliações de produtos na rede determinam compras dos brasileiros. <https://www.capterra.com.br/blog/848/avaliacoes-de-produtos-na-rede>
- Carvalho MM, Paladini EP (2012) Gestão da qualidade: teoria e casos. 2. ed. Rio de Janeiro, Elsevier.
- Castelli G (2010) Hospitalidade: a inovação na gestão das organizações prestadoras de serviços. São Paulo: Saraiva.
- Castelli G (2003) Administração hoteleira. 9. ed. Caxias do Sul: EDUCS, 2003.
- Surprenant C, Churchill G (1982) An investigation into the determinants of customer satisfaction, *Journal of Marketing Research*. November, 1982, Vol. XIX.
- Deming EW (1993) O Americano que ensinou a qualidade total aos japoneses. Rio de Janeiro: Record, 1993.
- Feigenbaum AV (1994) Controle da qualidade total. São Paulo: Makron Books.
- Gianesi IGN, Corrêa HL (2006) Administração Estratégica de Serviços: operações para a satisfação de clientes. São Paulo: Atlas, 233 pp.
- Ishikawa KT (1986) Total Quality Control. In: MISHIMURA, M. Estratégia e Administração da Qualidade. São Paulo: IMC Internacional Sistemas Educativos.
- Juran JM (1951) Juran's Quality Handbook. New York: McGraw-Hill.

- Kotler P(1999) Marketing para o século XXI: como criar, conquistar e dominar mercados. São Paulo: Futura.
- Magalhães DT, Veloso CM, Sousa BB (2020) Lealdade dos hóspedes nacionais: um estudo aplicado à hotelaria do Douro. *Journal of Tourism & Development* 34: 191–207. <https://doi.org/10.34624/rtd.v0i34.22363>
- Mundo das Marcas (2013) Tripadvisor. Mundo das marcas, 22 Abr. de 2013. <https://mundodasmarcas.blogspot.com/2013/04/tripadvisor.html>
- Petry TRE, Pickler CM, Tomelin CA (2016) A percepção dos hóspedes de negócios quanto ao desempenho da qualidade dos serviços prestados nos hotéis de Florianópolis: uma análise a partir do conteúdo gerado no website Booking.com. *Revista Turismo - Visão e Ação - Eletrônica* 18(2): 327–352. <https://doi.org/10.14210/rtva.v18n2.p327-352>
- Prefeitura Municipal de João Pessoa (2018) Taxa de ocupação da rede hoteleira de João Pessoa atinge 72,9% para o feriadão da Semana Santa. Prefeitura de João Pessoa, 26 de Março de 2018. <http://antigo.joaopessoa.pb.gov.br/taxa-de-ocupacao-da-rede-hoteleira-de-joao-pessoa-atinge-729-para-o-feriado-da-semana-santa>
- Souza SMDOS (2018) Gestão da qualidade e produtividade. S. Universitária, p. 9 .São Paulo.
- Zhou L, Ye S, Pearce PL, Wu MY (2014) Refreshing hotel satisfaction studies by reconfiguring customer review data. *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 38: 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2013.12.004>